
LACTOGENIC EFFECT OF PALM WINE IN ALBINO WISTAR RATS USING OXYTOCIN AND BODY WEIGHT AS BIOMARKERS.

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Introduction: Lactation is a critical physiological process in mammals, regulated by hormones such as oxytocin that facilitate milk ejection. In some cultures, consumption of palm wine is believed to enhance lactation, yet scientific evidence supporting this claim is limited. Investigating how palm wine influences lactation and hormonal regulation is essential to better understand its potential effects on maternal and offspring health. **Objective:** This study aimed to evaluate the effect of palm wine on serum oxytocin levels, maternal and pup body weights, and mammary gland number in lactating albino Wistar rats. **Methodology:** This is a quantitative, experimental, controlled research study. Ten lactating albino Wistar rats and their sixty pups were randomly assigned into two groups of five animals each: a control group receiving no treatment, and an experimental group receiving 10 ml/kg of palm wine orally daily for 21 days. Animals were monitored for behavior, feeding patterns, physical activity, and overall health throughout the study period. Blood samples were collected on days 1, 7, and 21 to quantify serum oxytocin concentrations, while maternal and pup body weights and mammary gland numbers were recorded. Statistical analysis was performed using Student's t-test, with significance set at $p < 0.05$, respecting the ethical principles of research with experimental animals. **Results:** Palm wine administration resulted in a significant decrease in serum oxytocin levels ($p < 0.05$) and a significant reduction in pup body weight ($p < 0.05$) compared to controls. Maternal body weight and mammary gland number were not significantly affected ($p > 0.05$). No behavioral or physiological abnormalities were observed, indicating that the treatment was well tolerated. **Conclusion:** It is concluded that palm wine consumption suppresses oxytocin secretion and reduces offspring growth in lactating Wistar rats, while maternal weight and mammary gland development remain largely unaffected. These findings suggest that palm wine may negatively influence lactational hormonal regulation and offspring development. Further studies are recommended to elucidate the mechanisms underlying these effects. Strengthening research on the physiological and toxicological effects of traditional alcoholic beverages is essential to better understand their potential health impacts.

Palavras-chave: Oxytocin Hormone, Lactation, Hormonal Regulation.